

GNOSEOLOGY – PHILOSOPHICAL TEACHING ABOUT KNOWLEDGE.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8416402>

Abstract: Knowledge of the Universe and its laws is a matter directly related to the philosophical worldview. That is why the question of knowledge of the world has always been at the center of attention of philosophy. Ancient philosophers also recognized the possibility of knowing the world. For example, Democritus , the founder of atomic theory, claims that it is possible to understand the Universe and achieve truth. It shows the role of emotions and thinking in the process of cognition, simply and clearly.

Key words: intuition, perception, memory, imagination, knowledge, antiquity, fanaticism, agnosticism, skepticism

Farabi, one of the thinkers of Central Asia, said that the problem of knowledge is part of the problem of determining the essence of man. He considers man to be the subject of knowledge, and the surrounding nature to be the object of knowledge of reality. According to Al- Farabi , a perceived thing exists before the senses, and a cognizable thing also exists before the knowledge associated with it. According to his definition, a person receives his knowledge from the outside, from surrounding phenomena. This process involves many tools and methods: intuition, perception, memory, imagination and most importantly logic, reason and speech. With the help of these tools man created science.

Beruni's legacy shows that from his earliest works to his later, we see that he was deeply interested in human knowledge. According to Beruni , the basis of knowledge, the source of our knowledge about the world is sensory knowledge obtained through the senses. Without intuition, our knowledge of the Universe would be impossible.

Process of cognition. According to Beruni , it is necessary to be free from old age, fanaticism, personal prejudices, subjectivism, to rely on nature itself, on irrefutable evidence of observation and experience: the process of knowing nature begins with feeling and goes back to thinking, to known things and phenomena, knowledge develops, but It is impossible to know everything during the lifetime of one generation.

In the theory of knowledge of the great scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina, the mind is an active creative force and an instrument of knowledge, but the material world and its laws are studied in the process of experience: concepts about objects and

events appear. The human mind increases its knowledge through sensory perception through the process of long and hard work.

In his philosophical views, Alisher Navoi mainly recognizes the possibility of knowing the material world. The source of his knowledge is reality; everything that exists in the world consists of the object (object) of our feelings. The great humanist emphasizes that knowledge is the source of human happiness.

In the history of philosophy, there are various directions that deny the possibility of knowing the laws of development of nature and society, as well as views that recognize the knowledge of such a world. Those who deny and doubt that the world can be known, that our knowledge is correct and certain, are the doctrines of agnosticism and skepticism. (Agnosticism is a Greek word, a - denial, gnosos - knowledge). The oldest form of agnosticism is skepticism. (skepticism about knowledge).

The greatest representatives of agnosticism are the English philosopher David Hume and the German philosopher Immanuel Kant. According to Hume, a person cannot go beyond the limits of his feelings, he can only know his feelings. The real cannot know reality at all. For Kant, unlike Hume, there is a “thing in itself”, which cannot be known in the objective world outside of human consciousness and feelings; the “thing in itself” is outside space and time, and cannot be known in its entirety. Kant says that the world of phenomena that can be known by man is “things that exist for us” and can be known by human reason and the means of science.

“What is for us” and “The thing in itself” are phenomena that can be known through a mixed effect on the senses, which a person organizes with his innate a priori concepts.

In general, Kant’s theory of knowledge is completely confused, unscientific and reactionary and aimed at denying the prospects for the development of science, taking into account its essence.

Philosophers of the 17th–18th centuries. (English Bacon, French Descartes, Diderot, Holgbach , Helgvetius) play an important role in the development of the theory of knowledge. They sharply criticize agnosticism and spectism and emphasize that it is possible to know the Universe. However, there were certain shortcomings in their views. For example, their theory of knowledge, being of a metaphysical nature, could not demonstrate the dialectical unity of the emotional and rational sides of knowledge. They failed to find that the cognitive process is inconsistent. They also failed to understand the role of human practice in social history and denied the role of conscious human activity.

It is known that the objective world, its objects and phenomena are the only source of knowledge. However, some philosophers and religious teachings recognize a certain mystical, seemingly non-human consciousness as the source of knowledge (“Absolute Idea”, “universal spirit”, etc.). From their point of view, man is not capable of cognizing the essence of natural phenomena and social life; he is only capable of recording and classifying the results of God's creation.

“Cognition is the process of perceiving the material world in the human mind.”

Humanity, its social practices and the development of knowledge are dispelling the agnosticism that limits knowledge. For example, modern natural science, especially physics, has made great strides in studying the structure and properties of atomic nature. The disintegration of the atom, the use of the internal energy of the atom, the interconnection of atomic nuclear particles, knowledge of the microworld in general, discoveries in astronomy and biology confirm the correctness of the theory of knowledge of scientific philosophy.

A person's ability to know is not limited, but in each specific historical period he does not know all the things and events that he wants to know, but only those that are possible to know, and later he knows what he did not know. But it should be said that there is no limit to human knowledge, because the infinity of the macro-micro universe shows the infinity of human knowledge.

2. What is knowledge? Knowledge is the process of interiorization of the material world in the human mind; more precisely, knowledge is not a simple mechanical reflection, but a reflection of things and events of the objective world in the human brain in the form of generalized, abstract, scientific concepts. Recognition of the materiality of the world and the introduction of the laws of its development into human consciousness forms the basis of the scientific philosophy of the theory of knowledge. The laws of science are nothing more than the conclusion of objective processes occurring in nature and society independently of human consciousness. The theory of knowledge of philosophy is based mainly on the following.

- the objective universe exists outside of our intuitions and ideas, the objective universe is the source of human intuition and imagination;
- it is possible to know the laws of the human world and its development. A person perceives the content of the world independent of him in his intuition, imagination and concepts.

Therefore, the external world, all things and events in it influence the senses and create sensory images. The subjective reflection of the objective world is formed in sensory images and concepts. This is why the theory of knowledge is called

the theory of knowledge. The theory of knowledge requires the correct solution of the relationship between object and image, object and subject. Because in the process of cognition the dialectic of object and subject plays an important role. This is an object, that is, a process associated with a person. Without a person there can be no process of knowledge. The role of the subject in scientific knowledge is that it reveals the natural connections in which the goal exists. Approaches to the object both practically and theoretically.

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